

Government/Legislative Frameworks and International Protocols on Climate Change in Nigeria

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PAPER KEYWORDS

Climate Change, Goals of Climate Change, Effects of Climate Change, Adaptation.

ABSTRACT

Climate change is a global phenomenon that is notably unpredictable. Nigeria, in recognition of the threat it poses to the environment, endorsed the Paris International Protocol on climate change, ratified by the legislature thereafter, and concluded with the enactment of the Climate Change Act, 2021, thus standing as the framework for climate change policy plans, formulation, development, implementation, evaluation, and coordination of all actions on climate change at all levels of governance for the attainment of resilient, sustainable development. The objective of this study is to highlight government/legislative frameworks and international protocols on climate change in Nigeria. The study adopts international regime theory that explains principles deployed to solve global problems and cooperation of the independent states on issues like climate change. The study gathered data from secondary sources and personal observations, and these data were analysed based on their context. The study revealed that Nigeria's endorsement of the Paris Agreement in 2015 and subsequent actions leading to the legislation were constitutional. The Act establishes the National Council on Climate Change as the implementation agency on climate change with powers to administer, fund, and coordinate all the ministries, departments, and agencies; sanctions all acts of sabotage on climate change mitigation and adaptation measures, among others. The study recommends public awareness/education on climate change occurrences, reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, removal of carbon dioxide from the atmosphere into reservoirs, upholding adaptation measures, and boosting renewable energy on a large scale by the year 2030, thus minimising the quantity of sunlight reaching the earth.

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19875468>

1.1. Introduction

Climate change is a spectacular occurrence that affects humans, the environment, and all other organisms on the planet. Thus, the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (1992) defined Climate Change as “a change of climate attributed directly or indirectly to human activity that alters the composition of the global atmosphere and which is in addition to natural climate variability observed over comparable time periods.”

Holmes (2015) asserted that climate change has caused adverse effects on the physical environment and in the operation of socio-economic systems, human health and

welfare, among others. Scientific and expert views about the impact of climate change on humans and their environment have made it imperative for a responsive and responsible government to devise means to reduce the effects of climate change on society, considering that the first responsibility of a government is to protect the lives and properties of its citizens.

Mohammad (2021) stated that since climate change is inevitable, complex, and dynamic, it requires dimensional and multi-sectoral mitigation and adaptation initiatives through a vibrant and forceful policy framework to overcome its challenges. Similarly, the federal government have recognised climate change as a threat to national sustainable development, thus endorsed the Paris Agreement Protocol on Climate Change. Accordingly, enlists some sectors vulnerable to climate change - agriculture and food security, forests and biodiversity, water resources, energy and infrastructure, health, human settlement, industry and commerce, transportation and communication. It was also discovered that climate change affects the education system, immigration and emigration, security, and natural hazards. While the most vulnerable regions are the coastal areas in the extreme southern part and erosion and desertification-prone areas in the southeastern and northern parts of the country, respectively, likewise, the vulnerable groups include farmers, fisher folks, the elderly, women, children, persons with disabilities and poor people. The afore-mentioned classification, attributed to climate change pushed the erstwhile Buhari Administration (2015-2023) to popularise climate change phenomenon, and based on section 20 of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (CFRN) 1999 endorsed the Paris Agreement Climate Change Protocol in the year 2015, later ratified by the legislature in March 2017, and enacted the Climate Change Act, 2021 on 17th November, 2021 (Udo Udoma & Bello-Osagie (2021).

Mohammad (2021) maintained that the passage of the Climate Change Bill into law triggered the development of relevant climate change policies and plans, implementation framework, and programme of action that cut across some sectors and institutions in the country, namely: Agriculture, Environment, Energy, Health, Oil and Gas, Water, Waste, Transport, among others; as well as private and public bodies. The programme of actions comprises short, medium and long-term strategies to manage inevitable climate change, and as a contribution to stabilize Green House Gas concentrations in the atmosphere, thus building a climate-resilient Nigeria.

Udo Udoma & Bello-Osagie (2021) added that the Buhari Administration drew up several strategies as safety mechanisms for the protection of the Nigerian environment and ecosystem on one hand, and tackled problems arising from climate change. These were national responses to the challenge of climate change in selected sectors of national development, and demonstrated that Climate change is significantly affecting Nigeria's socio-economic development, including the natural ecosystems.

This paper examines the government/legislative frameworks and international protocols on climate change subscribed to by the federal government of Nigeria, noting that climate change has become a phenomenon affecting the socio-economic impacts and environment.

Climate change is an unavoidable phenomenon that affects man and the environment globally, and Nigeria is not exempted. According to Holmes (2015), the variation in climate patterns arises from human and non-human activities such as Green House Gases emission, deforestation, industrial processes, among others, causing global warming, deforestation, drought, degradation, reduction in water supply, mass displacement, floods, human health and welfare. Mohammad (2021) affirmed that Nigeria government [Buhari Administration (2015-2023) era], in response to the threat posed by climate change to sustainable development, endorsed the Paris International Agreement on climate change in 2015, followed by the legislature's ratification in 2017, and the enactment of the Climate Change Act, on 17th November, 2021. These activities compel this study, hence the examination of government/legislative frameworks and international protocols on climate change in Nigeria.

Conceptual Underpinning

Australian Academy of Science (2015) described climate change as a change in the pattern of weather, and related changes in oceans, land surfaces and ice sheets, occurring over time scales of decades or longer.

Hans and Debra (2022) defined climate change as a variation in the pattern of climate over time, which results from human or man-related activity. These scholars claimed that the change affects the conditions of oceans, land surfaces, and the entire surroundings, attributed the causes of climate change to man's activities like burning of fuels, coal, oil gas, among others for energy; cutting of trees (deforestation); industrial processes; intensive agricultural activities; transportation; and maintained that all the afore-mentioned activities releases heat Green House Gases (carbon dioxide, methane, and other poisonous elements) to the atmosphere. The gases are recycled to the environment. The consequences of man's various activities lead to global warming, that is, an increase in atmospheric temperature, which, according to Hans and Debra, is dated to centuries; consequently, suggested the need for the reduction of all activities leading to the burning of gaseous elements into the atmosphere.

Mohammad (2021) remarked that climate change is a big challenge that confronts the human race and requires multi-sectoral adaptation strategies to confront the menace. Mohammad speculated that the threat posed by climate change to national sustainable development influenced the Nigerian government to subscribe to the Paris Agreement on National Climate Change Policy and Response Strategy (NCCPRS). The global discourse on climate change has evolved, leading to the adoption of new initiatives that have been domesticated to guide national responses to reducing the impact of climate change and adaptation to manage the challenge.

Sources of Climate Change

Holmes (2015) declared that atmospheric concentrations of carbon dioxide, methane and nitrous oxide began to rise around two hundred years ago. Some of the factors responsible includes: increases in atmospheric carbon dioxide and other long-lived greenhouse gases (methane, nitrous oxide and halocarbons); increases in short-lived greenhouse gases (mainly ozone) changes to land cover (replacement of darker forests with paler croplands and grasslands); increases in aerosols (tiny particles in the atmosphere); solar fluctuations (changes in the brightness of the sun); and volcanic

eruptions. Climate change affects land, air, ocean, and geographical spaces. Holmes declared further that “physical principles established more than a century ago tell us that certain trace gases in the atmosphere, such as carbon dioxide and water vapour, restrict the radiant flow of heat from Earth to space. This mechanism is known as the ‘greenhouse effect’, which keeps the Earth’s surface and lower atmosphere warmer than they would otherwise be. The gases involved are called ‘greenhouse gases’. An increase in greenhouse gas concentrations raises the temperature of the surface.” Alausa (2025) grouped sources of climate change as human and non-human, reiterated that human sources include activities such as burning oil into the air; deforestation; agricultural activities, industrial processes; poor waste disposal; urbanisation, modernisation, transportation, etc. The non-human source, on the other hand, comprises volcanic eruptions, solar activities, greenhouse gas effects, among others.

Goals of Climate Change

According to Hans and Debra (2022), the goals of climatic change situation relate to the reduction of adverse effects of climate change on individual sectors such as health, water, food security, jobs and employment, poverty eradication and social equity, biodiversity and ecosystem services at international, national and local levels. These scholars described the goals of climate change as two, namely: reduction of risk and exposure to climate change, strengthening resilience, enhancing well-being, and building the capacity to anticipate and respond successfully to climate change. Hans and Debra (2022) affirmed that existing international frameworks provide a high-level direction for coordinating, financing and assessing progress toward these goals. However, specifying the goals for specific adaptation actions is not straightforward because the impacts of climate change affect people and nature in diverse ways and require different adaptation actions. Thus, goals that accompany these actions are diverse. The goals can relate to health, water or food security, jobs and employment, poverty eradication and social equity, biodiversity and ecosystem services at international, national and local levels,

Effects of Climate Change

WHO Regional Office for Africa (2015) in the study on “Effects of Climate Change on the Social & Environmental Determinants of Health in Africa” carried out in Congo in the year 2015, enumerated that climate change affects both the low and high members of the community, including all sectors in the setting. The negative effects of climate change lead to “extreme weather events, a decrease in access to safe water, a decrease in air quality, a decrease in food security, [as well as] an increase in climate-sensitive diseases.”

Climate Change, Development, and Future

Holmes (2015) warned that continuity in the emission of greenhouse gas will result to upsurge in the average world air temperature to 4° Celsius by the year 2100. However, if emissions are reduced, there is a chance that global average warming will not exceed 2°C and similarly, other impacts will be limited. With continued strong growth in carbon dioxide emissions, much more warming is expected. Holmes suggested that the need to develop ways to reduce the burning of carbon dioxide into the air is essential.

Adaptation to Climate Change

Holmes (2015) enumerated adaptation as measures put in place to check actual or expected climate or its effects. The success of adaptation depends on the extent to which adaptation actions achieve their respective goals of reducing climate risk, increasing resilience and pursuing other climate-related societal goals. Holmes considered adaptation in two ways – global and local. Global view refers to actions anticipated to make significant contributions to meeting SDGs, such as ending extreme poverty, hunger and discrimination, and reducing risks to ecosystems, water, food systems, human settlements, and health and well-being. Local view, on the other hand, consists of actions that help communities to meet their diverse goals, including reducing anticipated current and future risks, enhancing capacity to adapt and transform, to yield benefits greater than costs and serving vulnerable populations.

ALausa (2025) emphasised measures to adjust to climate change as follows: uphold measures put in place to counter climate change; embark on smart agriculture; mass tree planting; preservation of water; and development of plans to mitigate the effects of climate change.

Adaptation Evaluation

These attributes of adaptation success can be assessed throughout the adaptation process of planning, implementation, monitoring & evaluation, adjustment and learning. However, at the same time, the success of many adaptation actions depends strongly on context and time. For instance, the effectiveness of adaptation will depend on the success of GHG mitigation efforts, as adaptation has strong synergies and trade-offs with mitigation efforts (Hans and Debra, 2022).

International protocols on climate change

Gilbert and Mark (2018) explained protocol as the term for establishing conduct to avoid conflicts and arguments, whereas international protocol concerns itself with conduct between industrial partners and the developing countries. In brief, a protocol is a means of creating a partnership between entities to forge a mutual relationship based on expressed terms and conditions.

Hamalai (2017) regarded partnership as one pillar on which the implementation of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) depends; that partnership facilitates the achievement of global solidarity for sustainable development.

The SDGs are a development framework which countries have subscribed to and are expected to implement for the realisation of economic prosperity. The fear of the negative consequences of climate change on the environment led Nigeria to endorse the Paris International Protocol Agreement on Climate Change on September 22, 2015 and also in March 2017, subscribed to the Protocol. In addition, the federal government enacted the Climate Change Act, 2021, on November 17th 2017. This subsequently permits the federal government to implement the protocol. Implicitly, Nigeria pledges to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Other additional obligations to fulfil by the federal

government include: achieving net-zero emissions between the years 2050 – 2070; reduction of emissions by 32.2% by 2030 and 47% conditionally; renewable energy shares in the power mix of the federation by 2030; and obtaining climate finance between US\$ 20 – 25 billion by 2023 through green bonds and partnership (www.journals.sagepub.com, www.premuimtimesng.com).

Components of the Paris International Protocol on Climate Change

Ichuchukwu (2025) enumerated the components of the Paris Agreement as follows:

- a. *Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs)*. This portion requires members' countries to submit climate plans and targets on specific sectors – Agriculture, Energy, Health, etc.
- b. *Global Stocktake*: this part requires carrying out regular evaluation and submission of progress reports at intervals on the aforementioned sector, one by one.
- c. *Climate Finance*. This part emphasises the funds promised by the industrialised/developed nations to support developing countries.
- d. *Adaptation and mitigation*, this part provides support for countries to adapt and reduce emissions, sectorally.
- e. *Transparency Framework*, this section of the Paris Agreement tracks progress and submits a progress report on emissions rate in each member's country.
- f. *Loss and damage*, this portion concerns the provision of permanent climate impact.

Government/Legal Framework on Climate Change in Nigeria

The preliminary responsibility of a government globally is the protection of the lives and properties of the citizens, and by the provisions of Nigeria's constitution also embraces the environment inhabited by the populace. Specifically, section 14 (2) (b) the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (CFRN) 1999 (as altered), states that "the security and welfare of the people shall be the primary purpose of government", and section 20 (CFRN) 1990 (as altered), provides that "The state shall protect and improve the environment and safeguard the water, air and land, forest and wild life of Nigeria." Similarly, section 12 empowers the Nigerian National Assembly to ratify a treaty to have the force of law. The afore-mentioned constitutional provisions, among others, authorise the National Assembly to enact relevant laws to maintain the environment and promote the surroundings.

Holmes (2015) avowed that the impact of climate change on man and its environment makes it imperative for a responsible and responsive government to devise means to reduce the effects of climate change on society in concurrence with the provisions of the country's Constitution.

Legal framework on climate change refers to rules and regulations that provide duties and obligations to governments, organisations, individuals and parties involved in climate change. Hans and Debra (2022) stated the components of legal frameworks as the Constitution, legislation, regulations, and contracts; narrated their relationships to one another and thus termed them as legal architecture. Relying on Hans and Debra's

(2022) architecture, this paper outlines the federal government of Nigeria's legal framework on climate change as follows:

- ✓ Constitution: Section 20 (CFRN) 1990 (as altered), vests the federal government of Nigeria with the responsibility "to protect and improve the environment and safeguard the water, air and land, forest and wildlife of Nigeria". Nigeria's 1999 Constitution enumerates the political structure, institutions, checks and balances within the democratic system in practice, and human rights provisions, environmental protection, civil legal process, and labour standards. Nigeria establishes specific rules governing many sectors, specific provisions on key policy issues, including formulas for resource revenue-sharing, among others.
- ✓ Policy/Legislation: In recognition of section 4 CFRN 1999 (as altered), that places legislative powers of the Federal Republic of Nigeria in the National Assembly of the Federation; section 12 that authorises treaty ratification such as Paris International Protocol Agreement on Climate Change, International Human Rights Laws, African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights, environmental statutes and international Conventions to which Nigeria endorses, and national laws: The Child Rights Act, The Violence Against Persons Prohibition Act and Discrimination Against Persons with Disabilities (Prohibition) Act, among others, the National Assembly enacted Climate Change Act, 2021 as the statute for implementation of climate change in Nigeria (Clean 2021). Udo Udoma & Bello-Osagie (2021) reported some vital points of the Climate Change Act (CCA) as follows:
 - ✓ creates a Council on Climate Change and empowers the Council to: develop policies and make decisions on all matters on climate change, manage the implementation of CCA provisions; administer the climate change fund; collaborate with the Federal; Inland Revenue Service for taxation; coordinate the implementation of sectoral targets and guidelines for the regulation of Green House Gas emissions and other anthropogenic causes of climate change; and establishes the Secretariat and a Director-General as the administration head.
 - ✓ Establishes funding sources for the Climate Change, namely: Consolidated Revenue Fund; subventions, grants and donations, fees for services rendered or publications made by the Council; donor agencies; Nationally Determined Contributions; fines and charges from private and public entities for flouting their Climate Change mitigation and adaptation obligations; carbon tax and emissions trading; and other funds as the council may be prescribed; and prescriptions of the applications towards the realization of CCA goals.
 - ✓ Mandates the Federal Ministries of the Environment and National Planning to set the carbon budget; maintain the average increase in global temperature within 2 degrees Celsius; and make a concerted effort to limit the temperature increase to 1.5 degrees Celsius above pre-industrial levels;
 - ✓ Directs the Secretariat to liaise with the Ministry of Environment, Federal Ministry of Budget and National Planning, to formulate a National Climate Change Action Plan every five years, and the first plan shall be produced within 12 (twelve) months from the inception of the Act.

- ✓ Establish a climate change desk for ensuring integration of climate change activities into their core mandate, and make regulations, impose obligations relating to climate change on relevant entities, vary or revoke any such obligations, where necessary.
- ✓ applicable to all Federal Government institutions, public and private entities in Nigeria, and its goal is to develop and implement mechanisms
- ✓ Empowers the Federal Ministry of Environment to set up a registry with sub-national nodes for capturing REDD+ activities in Nigeria, including updates on Forest Reference Emission Level (FREL). In addition, the Council should provide fiscal support for REDD+ activities.
- ✓ Sanctions any negative efforts towards mitigation and the adaptation measures as an offence that is liable to a penalty, determined by the Council.

Based on the legislative practice, the National Assembly contributes to developmental events through creation of standing committee on Climate Change in both chambers; ensuring accountability on climate change issues; conduct legislative scrutiny and oversight treaties arising from UN Framework Convention on climate change; oversight of the National Council on climate change, debate climate change mitigation and adoption policy, policy implementation, among others; and allocate funds annually in the Appropriation Act, which the Council have been enjoying since year 2021 till date. As part of legislative support, the Nigerian National Assembly has similarly established a standing committee on Renewable Energy in both Houses to oversee all renewable energy issues like bioenergy, geothermal, hydropower, ocean, solar and wind energy and related institutions (Standing Orders Eleven Edition).

- ✓ Regulation/Rules/Model Contract: In Nigeria, the climate change policy is domiciled in the Federal Ministry of Environment. Muhammad (2021) enumerated that the federal government established the Department of Climate Change to oversee all matters relating to climate change, under the supervision of the Federal Ministry of Environment, in the year 2012 when the development of the National Climate Change Policy and Response Strategy (NCCPRS) started. Similarly, the Ministry, through the Department, anchors global discourse on climate change, leading to the adoption of new initiatives that have been domesticated, guiding national response to reducing the impact and adapting to the challenge. The Ministry also serves as the Secretariat for the Inter-Ministerial Committee on Climate Change (ICCC), which comprises Ministries, Departments and Agencies of government, individuals, private organisations, development partners, and relevant stakeholders, and carries out revision of the National Climate Change Policy as appropriate. In addition, the Federal Ministry of Environment liaises with other line ministries to draw up environmental-related policies to regulate the sector and, consequently, implement rules created by an executive body of government to make legislation practical. For example, the Environmental Impact Assessment is to provide regulations on the effect of investment on the immediate surroundings. Section 4 of CFRN 1999 (as altered) authorises the National Assembly to provide different legislation on areas including Mining, Oil Prospective Licence, Procurement, Concession,

among others. Each of these legislations describes how, when and where interested business prospects must register their concern and submit for further processes. Furthermore, the legislation will enumerate guidelines or other terms for registration and scope. In Nigeria, each Ministry has distinct regulations, responsibilities, and administrative powers (based on the enabling act) to create rules and guidelines with or without legislative approval.

- ✓ **Contracts:** The Climate Control Act, 2021 (CCA), encourages relationships with other institutions of government to attain the goals of the law. For instance, the CCA Secretariat is mandated to liaise with the Federal Ministry of Environment, Federal Ministry of Budget and National Planning, Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS), and other Ministries, Departments, and Agencies of the federal government, public and private organisations to accomplish the goals of the CCA.

Agency for the Implementation of Climate Change Legislation

Udo Udoma & Bello-Osagie (2021) confirmed that section 3 of the Climate Change Act (CCA) establishes the National Council on Climate Change (Council) and vests the Council with the powers to develop policies and make decisions on climate change in Nigeria. The Act prescribes a Director-General as the head with the role of administration, scientific, and technical functions of Ministries, Departments, and Agencies, public and private entities across Nigeria; and reiterates the purpose of the Council as policy development and coordinating implementation sector by sector for the attainment of low carbon emission and a sustainable environment.

Mohammad (2021) itemised some existing policies that have direct and indirect bearings on the climate change challenge under various MDAs that target the reduction of emissions and promotion of sustainable development in Nigeria, including:

- a. National Adaptation Strategy and Plan of Action on Climate Change for Nigeria (NASPA-CCN) 2011
- b. National Renewable Energy and Energy Efficiency Policy (NREEEP) 2015;
- c. National Gas Policy (2017)
- d. National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (NBSAP) 2016;
- e. National Forest Policy (NFP) 2010;
- f. National Forestry Action Plan (NFAP) 1996;
- g. National Policy on Environmental 2016;
- h. Nigeria Agricultural Policy 2001;
- i. Agricultural Promotion Policy (APP) 2016 – 2020;
- j. National Climate Change Policy and Response Strategy (NCCPRS) 2012;
- k. National Policy on Drought and Desertification (NPDD) 2007;
- l. Great Green Wall for the Sahara And Sahel Initiative National Strategic Action Plan (GGWSAP) 2012;
- m. National Agricultural Resilience Framework (NARF) 2013;
- n. National Health Policy (2016);
- o. National Water Policy (2012);
- p. National Transport Policy (2016)
- q. Nigeria Industrial Revolution Plan (2014)
- r. National Gender Policy (2006),

s. REDD+ Strategy, 2019

Ichuchukwu (2025) reiterated some of the specific policies that the Council has developed for the reduction of climate change in recent times. These include:

- a. National Climate Change Policy (NCCP). This document explains the country's climate goals, priorities, and strategies for climate change reduction and adaptation.
- b. National Climate Change Action Plan (NCCAP). This policy states the strategies to curtail emissions.
- c. National Adaptation Plan (NAP), the policy focuses on resilience and adjustment capacity.
- d. Carbon Tax Policy aims at the reduction of emissions.
- e. Methane Guidelines for Oil and Gas Sector, which addresses the reduction of methane from oil and gas operations.
- f. National Forest Policy, this aims at reforestation, that is, to boost forest cover at a specific rate by the year 2023.
- g. Long-Term Low Emissions Development Strategy (LT-LEDS), which targets a zero emission by 2060.

Strategies to reduce the effects of Climate Change

Holmes (2015) said societies face choices about future climate change, and as such needs to manage the risks from future human-induced climate change, consequently, proffer four strategies to cope with climate change as follows: emissions reduction: reducing climate change by reducing greenhouse gas emissions; sequestration: removing carbon dioxide from the atmosphere into permanent geological, biological or oceanic reservoirs; adaptation: responding to and coping with climate change as it occurs, in either a planned or unplanned way; and solar geo-engineering: large-scale engineered modifications to limit the amount of sunlight reaching the earth, in an attempt to offset the effects of ongoing greenhouse gas emissions.

Similarly, Clean (2021) suggested measures to tackle the challenge of climate change by the federal government, such as the implementation of a climate change institutional framework; promotion of enabling climate policies; Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC); climate change financing; and donor-supported initiatives.

Hans and Debra (2022) recommended local and international measures of adaptation to climate change for specific action and to moderate harms. For instance: build against flooding, update building codes and land use plans, improve soil management, enhance water use efficiency, support migrants and take measures to reduce poverty. For natural systems, adaptation includes organisms changing behaviours, migrating to new locations and genetic modifications in response to changing climate conditions. The goals for these adaptation actions can relate to health, water or food security, jobs and employment, poverty eradication and social equity, biodiversity and ecosystem services, among others. Articulating the goals of adaptation thus requires engaging with the concepts of equity, justice and effectiveness at the international, national and local levels. International measures include implementation of the Paris Agreement and the SDGs for coordination, financing and assessing global progress to reduce vulnerability, strengthen resilience, enhance the capacity to anticipate and respond successfully, and

ensure the availability of necessary financial resources, as these processes and outcomes relate to climate change. Regarding the Sustainable Development Goals - SDG 13 on climate action requires partnership with developing partners to end extreme poverty by 2030, protect the planet and build more peaceful, just and inclusive societies. Other notable frameworks that identify climate change adaptation as an important global priority include the finance-oriented Addis Ababa Action Agenda and the New Urban Agenda.

1.2. Conclusion and Recommendations

The study revealed that the Federal Government of Nigeria endorsed the Paris International Protocol on Climate Change in the year 2015, and the legislature similarly ratified the treaty in March 2017. The arrangements were in line with the constitutional provisions (sections 20 and 12) of the Constitution of the Republic of Nigeria (CFRN) 1999. The legislature enacted the Climate Change Act, 2021, on 17th November, 2021, after domestication of the Treaty.

Section 3(1) of the Climate Change Act, 2021 establishes the National Council on Climate Change as the implementation Agency for climate change in Nigeria. The strategies to tackle climate change situation includes: promote climate change education in schools and sensitization of citizens throughout Nigeria; reduction of greenhouse gas emissions (GHG); removal of carbon dioxide from the atmosphere into biological/oceanic reservoirs, etc.; respond and coping with climate change as it occurs (adaptation); and promote renewable energy on large scale to limit the quantity of sunlight reaching the earth.

The recommendations include: implementation of a climate change institutional framework; promotion of enabling climate policies; setting and reporting nationally determined contribution (NDC) regularly; pursuing the climate change fund; and rallying for donor support initiatives.

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